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The fight against malaria: Diminishing gains and growing challenges

Justin M. Cohen^{1*}, Fredros Okumu^{2,3,4,5}, Bruno Moonen⁶

Affiliations:

¹Clinton Health Access Initiative; Boston, USA.

²Environmental Health and Ecological Science Department, Ifakara Health Institute; Ifakara, Tanzania.

³School of Public Health, Faculty of Health Sciences, University of the Witwatersrand; Johannesburg, South Africa.

⁴Institute of Biodiversity, Animal Health and Comparative Medicine, University of Glasgow; Glasgow, UK.

⁵School of Life Science and Bioengineering, The Nelson Mandela African Institution of Science and Technology; Arusha, Tanzania.

⁶Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation; Seattle, USA.

*Corresponding author. Email: jcohen@clintonhealthaccess.org

Abstract

Since the year 2000, historic reductions in malaria incidence and mortality have been driven by the widespread distribution of bed nets, drugs, and insecticides for the prevention, diagnosis, and treatment of malaria. Scale up of these tools has been enabled by an increase in malaria financing compounded by reductions in prices, yet these trends are unlikely to continue at the same rate. Rapid population growth in high-endemic areas requires procurement of more of these tools just to maintain current coverage, even as prices are likely to increase as resistance to drugs and insecticides forces shifts to newer products. Further progress towards the long-term goal of malaria eradication requires a combination of greater funding, more cost-effective resource allocation, and fundamental changes to the global malaria control strategy.

Main Text:

The 2020 World Malaria Report recently looked back on two decades of the global fight against malaria (1). Historic reductions in malaria incidence and mortality have occurred since the year 2000 (Fig. 1). From 2000 to 2015, global malaria incidence was reduced by 27%, but only by 2% in the years since then, leading the World Health Organization (WHO) to raise the alarm that progress has stalled and the world is at a crossroads in the fight against malaria (1). Where does the fight against malaria go from here?

Fig. 1. Global *P. falciparum* and *P. vivax* incidence. Shown are total cases, and mortality rates globally for the malaria pathogens *P. falciparum* and *P. vivax* as estimated by Malaria Atlas Project (www.malariaatlas.org) for 2000-2019. Shaded areas depict 95% confidence intervals. Illustrative counterfactuals (dotted lines) are linear extrapolations fit to 2000-2006, before the major scale-up of distribution of commodities such as drugs, insecticides, and bed nets.

This Review examines the gains achieved against malaria over two decades due to an historic increase in malaria financing compounded by dramatic reductions in the prices of key commodities. For years, these two trends enabled ever greater volumes of effective tools to be purchased and distributed throughout endemic regions, advancing towards the WHO's goal of universal coverage of at-risk populations. Today, this strategy continues to suppress malaria transmission and save tens of thousands of lives every year, but it appears insufficient to deliver further progress towards malaria eradication due to several critical trends. First, the effective tools that are the backbone of the current anti-malaria strategy such as drugs, insecticides, and

bed nets will likely grow more expensive in coming years as resistance to drugs and insecticides force shifts to newer products or combinations of products (2). Second, rapid population growth in high-endemic areas will demand procurement of these tools in ever greater numbers just to maintain current coverage. Further progress towards the ultimate long-term goal of malaria eradication requires some combination of greater funding, more cost-effective resource allocation, and fundamental strategic changes to recalibrate our malaria control efforts, still one of the best buys in global public health.

The universal coverage era

The African Summit on Roll Back Malaria in 2000 marked a turning point in the global fight against malaria after several decades of neglect. Following resuscitated interest in global malaria control in the 1990s through forums such as the 1992 Amsterdam Ministerial Conference on Malaria (3) and the first Global Burden of Disease study (4), the governments of 44 malaria-endemic African countries met in Abuja, Nigeria and signed a landmark agreement to halve malaria mortality. This Abuja Declaration committed countries to strengthening health systems to ensure at least 60% of those with malaria could access correct, affordable, and appropriate treatment; at least 60% of those at risk of malaria – particularly children under five years of age and pregnant women – would benefit from personal and community protective measures; and at least 60% of pregnant women would have access to chemoprophylaxis (5). The plan of action to achieve these targets was wide ranging and holistic, with a focus on strengthening health systems to better deliver malaria care and an array of preventative tools, while simultaneously building up the health work force, engaging the business community, and conducting operational research, among other aims. To fund these objectives, the declaration called for the cancellation of debts and allocation of at least \$1 billion in new resources.

The call for new funding to support the Roll Back Malaria objectives was fulfilled by the initiation of the Global Fund in 2002 (Fig. 2). Within contributions from the United States, European countries, and other donors, the fund distributed \$1.2 billion in malaria grants over its first five years of operations (6), an amount that it on average now distributes annually to malaria programs through 57 active country grants and five regional initiatives. Donor funding accelerated further with creation of the United States President's Malaria Initiative (PMI) in 2005. From an initial budget of \$30 million targeted to three African countries, PMI's bilateral

contributions grew to \$729 million across 24 countries in 2019 (7). Over these two decades, domestic financing of malaria programs by endemic countries also rose from an estimated \$556 million in 2000 to \$887 million in 2019, including estimated costs for patient care at public health facilities (1).

Fig. 2. Funding for malaria programs. Shown is funding for malaria programs by donor from 2000-2019 (in constant 2019 US\$) as compiled by WHO in the World Malaria Report (1).

These resources enabled impressive progress on part of the vision set forth in the Abuja Declaration, particularly the procurement and distribution of insecticide-treated bed nets. Provision of bed nets to protect pregnant women and children initially was viewed as a “quick win” (8) that could be achieved even in countries with weak health systems through campaign delivery. Distribution of nets only to vulnerable populations would, however, prove insufficient to realize communal protection (9) and reduce transmission (10). Doing so required a more audacious push to achieve and maintain “universal coverage,” as set forth in the revised 2008 Roll Back Malaria Global Malaria Action Plan (11). Seeking to cover the entire population resulted in high coverage among children and vulnerable groups (12) and theoretically offered protection even to those not sleeping under nets (9).

The drive for universal coverage led to a global scale-up of malaria commodities that continues to the present day (Fig. 3). Annual procurement of malaria bed nets increased from around 1

million in 2000 (13) to 230 million in 2020 (14). Malaria rapid diagnostic test procurement increased from <50 million in 2010, when the WHO revised its guidelines to recommend all suspected malaria cases be confirmed with a diagnostic test (15), to 419 million in 2020 (16). Only around 500,000 courses of artemisinin-based combination therapy (ACTs) were procured in 2001 (17) when they were first recommended for treatment of malaria in places where resistance to older drugs was prevalent (18). The WHO quality-assured market for ACTs peaked at 413 million in 2016 before declining thereafter with the termination of the Affordable Medicines Facility for malaria (1), although the overall market for ACTs is likely far larger (19). The number of people reportedly protected by indoor residual spraying of insecticide campaigns increased to a peak of 182 million in 2010 (20) before declining to under 100 million in 2020 (16). The number of children receiving at least one dose of sulfadoxine-amodiaquine for seasonal malaria chemoprevention increased from 170,000 in 2012 to over 33 million in 2020 (16). Of the \$3.2 billion in active malaria grants from the Global Fund as of March 2021, 74% was budgeted for commodities and their procurement and distribution (21). 48% of PMI’s 2020 malaria operational plans were budgeted for procurement and distribution of nets, insecticides, and drugs for seasonal chemoprevention, with an additional 15% for procurement of ACTs and rapid diagnostic tests.

Fig. 3. Volumes and prices of some key malaria commodities. *Blue bars are median prices reported in the Global Fund Price & Quality Reporting database, and error bars depict 25th and 75th percentiles. ACT prices were calculated according to the number of treatments per product pack. Red lines depict volumes procured in millions, as compiled from (13, 14) for bed nets, (1) for rapid diagnostic tests, and (1, 17) for ACTs. ACT volumes refer to the number procured by the public sector and private sector procurement through the Affordable Medicines Facility for malaria.*

Increased demand for malaria tools contributed to substantial reductions in their prices (Fig. 3). The Global Fund's Price and Quality Reporting (PQR) database is a voluntary reporting tool describing the types, volumes, and prices of commodities procured by Global Fund-supported programs (22). As a key source of information on the commodities purchased by the largest donor to malaria programs, the PQR provides visibility for historical pricing trends. As of March 2021, the PQR database included 2,250 orders of bed nets from 2003-2020, 4,483 orders of ACTs from 2006-2020, and 1,360 orders of malaria rapid diagnostic tests from 2007-2020. As volumes increased, median prices of bed nets (restricting to 2,181 orders placed in USD to avoid fluctuations in currency conversion rates) declined from a median of \$5.17 from 2004-2006 to <\$2 since 2016. Median prices of ACTs fell from >\$1 in 2006 and 2007 to <\$0.50 since 2018. Median prices of malaria rapid diagnostic tests rose from \$0.45 in 2007 to a peak of \$0.70 in 2011 before falling to a low of \$0.25 in 2015. The PQR also contains 231 orders for insecticides for indoor residual spraying from 2012-2020, but the smaller numbers of transactions and large variety of products and formulations in the database make it difficult to evaluate trends for insecticides.

These price reductions mean some of the most commonly procured malaria commodities now cost less than half of what they did in 2005, even as the donor funding available to procure them has more than tripled from <\$500 million to >\$1.6 billion. This more than six-fold increase in buying power has averted 10.6 million deaths and 1.7 billion illnesses from malaria between 2000-2019 (16). The majority of this preventative effect is likely attributable to the massive scale up of bed nets, with indoor residual spraying and ACTs in supporting roles (23). The fraction of the at-risk population sleeping under an insecticide-treated bed net increased to 43% across sub-Saharan Africa in 2020 from only 2% in 2000 (16), while the fraction of those seeking treatment for febrile illness in sub-Saharan Africa who reported receiving ACTs has increased from a median estimate of 38.9% from 2005-2011 to 75.7% from 2015-2019 (16).

Scale up of effective tools has achieved historic gains against malaria, but now that the so-called “quick wins” have been achieved, further reductions may prove more challenging. As coverage with health interventions increases, so do the incremental costs needed to further extend it to the remaining, harder-to-reach populations (24). For example, it has been estimated that increasing immunization coverage by 1% is about twice as expensive once 50% of the population is routinely immunized than when only 30% are routinely immunized (25). Similarly, analysis of malaria bed net procurement and resulting coverage suggests diminishing returns (26)---access to nets within populations at risk increases linearly with the number of nets distributed per capita until around 50% of the population has access, but much more slowly thereafter with incrementally higher cost due to distribution inefficiencies (27). As coverage gains become more incremental, achieving additional declines in incidence will become increasingly costly.

Population growth

The global population living in regions with endemic malaria transmission quadrupled from 709 million in 1900 to 2.8 billion in 2002, with growth rates greatest in the highest endemic regions (e.g., an almost 11x increase in populations living in regions with malaria prevalence >75%) (28). During the two decades that followed, populations at risk of malaria in Africa increased from 560 million in 2000 to 953 million in 2019 (a 70% increase), compared to a 28% increase for the remainder of the world’s at-risk populations (1).

Sub-Saharan Africa is projected to contribute the majority of the world’s population growth over the remainder of this century (29). The ten countries with the highest estimated malaria incidence rates in 2019---Benin, Burkina Faso, Liberia, Rwanda, Central African Republic, Nigeria, Sierra Leone, Mali, Democratic Republic of the Congo, and Mozambique (1)---are projected to have a median annual rate of population change of 2.69% from 2020 to 2025 (using the UN’s median projection, which is above sub-Saharan Africa’s overall rate of 2.52% and the global average of 0.98% (29). Highly endemic countries are thus the fastest growing regions of the fastest growing part of the world (Fig. 4). This population growth means that keeping up current coverage for prevention and treatment – i.e., not seeing lower coverage and thus potentially a rise in malaria rates – will require procuring approximately 2.7% more commodities each year over the next decade for the highest incidence countries. At this annual rate, by 2030 there will be 30% more

people to protect and treat for malaria in these high endemic countries, and thus 30% higher budget requirements for commodities if all else stays equal.

Fig. 4. National annual population growth rate by malaria incidence and population distribution of sub-Saharan Africa by *P. falciparum* prevalence. *The UN Medium Variant for 2020-2025 is shown at top for all countries in the world categorized according to their malaria incidence per 1,000 people in 2019, as estimated by the Malaria Atlas Project (www.malariaatlas.org). The orange line indicates the global growth rate. At bottom, the number of people in sub-Saharan Africa in 2020 living in areas that had at least that prevalence of *P. falciparum* in 2000 (before the start of intervention scale up, and thus a proxy for intrinsic risk) was calculated by overlaying gridded population estimates for 2020 from WorldPop (www.worldpop.org) with 2000 malaria prevalence data from the Malaria Atlas Project (www.malariaatlas.org).*

Commodity costs

Over the past two decades, scale up of vector control has involved predominantly pyrethroid-based insecticides, contributing to widespread insecticide resistance in the mosquito vector of malaria across Africa (30). In areas of known resistance, the WHO recommends switching to different classes of insecticides (31). In the case of bed-nets, products with the synergist

piperonyl-butoxide (PBO) can temporarily restore the action of the insecticide in areas where pyrethroid resistance is known to be conferred by a monooxygenase-based resistance mechanism (32). PBO bed nets may reduce malaria incidence and prevalence compared with conventional nets in those settings (33), and are therefore currently recommended for use in areas with moderate to high insecticide resistance. Demand for PBO nets is accordingly growing rapidly, from 5 million procured in 2018 (3% of nets going to sub-Saharan Africa) to 97 million in 2021 (44%), according to the Alliance for Malaria Prevention's Net Mapping Project. PBO nets procured in 2020 that were recorded in the PQR database had a median price of \$2.57 [interquartile range (IQR): \$2.53-\$2.61] compared to \$2.00 (IQR: \$1.99-\$2.00) for conventional pyrethroid nets, a 29% premium. Dual insecticide nets are also being trialed and may replace both pyrethroid and PBO nets, but prices are likely to be even higher for these products at least for the near term. In addition to insecticide resistance, concerns have also been raised that the focus on procuring the cheapest bed nets possible may have compromised their quality, including durability (34); higher quality bed nets may prove more effective but will come at a higher cost.

Resistance to the insecticides historically used for indoor residual spraying make this intervention less effective (35). New insecticide products for malaria vector control are now available to mitigate resistance, including the new class of neonicotinoids and new formulations such as Actellic 300CS (Syngenta Crop Protection Ag), Sumishield 50WG (Sumitomo Chemicals Co. Ltd), and Fludora Fusion (Bayer SAS). Adopting these next-generation products will be complicated by their higher prices, though efforts are underway to seek lower prices for these insecticides (36).

Resistance of the malaria pathogen *Plasmodium falciparum* to artemisinin-based combination drugs is widespread throughout Southeast Asia (37), and potential signs of resistance have recently been reported in Africa, including Rwanda (38), Tanzania (39), and Uganda (40). Resistance of *P. falciparum* to sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine, the drug used at large scale for intermittent presumptive treatment of children and pregnant women, is also widespread across much of Africa (41). Alternatives to artemisinin-based drugs are not yet available, but switching national treatment policies to select the ACT most likely to be effective given resistance data (42), deploying multiple first-line drugs (43), or using combinations with multiple partner drugs (44) may help to improve the effectiveness of treatment. However, the drugs most procured by

African malaria programs (and thus globally), artemether-lumefantrine and artesunate-amodiaquine, are also the cheapest of the ACTs today, and switching regimens comes with substantial operational and financial cost, as previously experienced when moving from chloroquine to sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine (45) and from sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine to ACTs (46). The Global Fund's pooled procurement mechanism reference pricing provides a child's dose of artemether-lumefantrine for \$0.27, and artesunate-amodiaquine for \$0.19 (47). In contrast, the cheapest children's doses of alternative ACTs such as pyronaridine-artesunate, dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine, and artesunate-mefloquine cost \$0.41, \$1.00, and \$1.22, respectively.

Parasite evolution is also compromising the effectiveness of the most commonly deployed type of malaria rapid diagnostic test (48), which identifies the presence of the histidine-rich protein 2 (HRP2) of *P. falciparum*. Loss of the *HRP2* gene, which so far has been observed at high rates in Eritrea, Ghana, Nicaragua, Peru, and Sudan (49), allows the parasite to evade detection by the cheapest rapid diagnostic tests available today. Alternative rapid diagnostic tests are available, but have historically been less accurate (50) and, likely due to lower demand, more expensive. Rapid diagnostic test prices may also increase for reasons other than pathogen evolution. In 2020, during the COVID-19 pandemic, manufacturing of rapid diagnostic tests for detecting SARS-CoV-2 were sold for substantially higher prices. This created a competing priority given they could be made on the same manufacturing lines as rapid diagnostic tests for malaria (51). Encouraging a steady supply of malaria rapid diagnostic tests in the future will thus require coordinated efforts to ensure a sustainable market, likely including accepting higher prices.

New tools for fighting malaria may become widely available in the coming years, but they will stretch malaria budgets even further. In particular, the RTS,S/AS01 vaccine recently became the first vaccine against any human parasitic infection to be recommended by the WHO. With efficacy of around 40% and a likely initial cost of around \$20 for the 4-dose regimen plus around \$11-\$13 in delivery costs per child protected (52), the vaccine is unlikely to be as cost-effective as other malaria control interventions (53). Even a modestly effective vaccine has the potential to avert large numbers of clinical cases if deployed preferentially to highest endemic settings (54), but it may further strain malaria budgets given the WHO recommendation that it should be used in addition to existing malaria interventions and not as a replacement.

Keeping up with the Red Queen

In ecology, “Red Queen dynamics” refer to how organisms must continually evolve and adapt to survive (55). The name refers to the character in Lewis Carroll’s *Through the Looking Glass* who tells Alice that “it takes all the running you can do, to keep in the same place” (56). To keep malaria in the same place will require maintaining current coverage for drugs and bed nets, even as populations at risk grow rapidly and the need to adopt next generation commodities reverses the trend of ever cheaper tools. Malaria expenditure increased by an annual average of 15% from 2000-2009 but only 1.6% from 2009-2017 (Fig 2). The 2017 estimate of donor and endemic government expenditure on malaria of \$3.3 billion is only about half of the \$6.4 billion estimated to be required for full implementation of the WHO’s Global Technical Strategy (57).

Maintaining current coverage with commodities will require available funding to keep up with growing populations at risk and increases in commodity prices.. For example, if commodity costs increase by 5% per year – which would mean the average \$2 price of bed nets today would rise to \$2.55 by 2025 (i.e., around the current price reported in the PQR for a PBO net) – in combination with the 2.52% annual population growth forecasted by the UN, funding would have to increase by >7.5% to keep pace. This is a nearly 5-fold greater rate than has occurred over the past decade. To keep pace, budget needs would have to double by 2030.

If program costs rise faster than donor funding, coverage with effective tools will decline, and malaria incidence will rise. Such an event would echo the resurgence experienced in the late years of the Global Malaria Eradication Program in the 1970s (58). At that time, increasing resistance of the malaria mosquito vector to cheap DDT insecticide necessitated changes to more expensive alternatives that increased the cost of indoor residual spraying from three to eight times (59). The cost increases occurred at the same time that donor support constricted. Both UNICEF and USAID ended most of their contributions to the program between 1970 and 1973 (60) as it became clear the global program was not on track to achieve its stated aims. As coverage necessarily fell due to reduced funds to buy more expensive products, a devastating resurgence of malaria occurred throughout much of the world (58).

Overcoming the challenges

The growth of at-risk populations coupled with at least near term increases in the cost of commodities will mean that today's strategy against malaria must evolve to avoid a reprisal of the failure of malaria control in the 1970s. Further reductions in malaria rates over the coming years are feasible, but we suggest they will require some combination of: (1) increases in available funding, (2) more cost-efficient deployment of today's tools and strategies guided by high-quality disease surveillance, (3) strengthened health systems to prevent mortality and drive sustainable reductions in transmission, (4) better engagement of the private sector, and (5) investment in non-commodity-based approaches and transformative technologies to fundamentally change malaria risk.

Increase funding. Substantial growth in funding for malaria programs and supportive systems from donor and domestic sources could enable maintenance of coverage or even outpace current trends if the new funding were optimally targeted. After all, similar concerns about the implausibility of sufficient donor funding were raised over a decade ago when it was proposed to pursue universal bed net coverage, yet extraordinary growth in donor contributions followed (61). After a record replenishment, Global Fund distributions for malaria grants reached an all-time high in 2020 of over \$1.4 billion (6), and USAID's 2020 budget of \$770 million was also its largest yet. Excitement about the new malaria vaccine could also encourage new contributions.

An important opportunity for malaria is to leverage increasing global enthusiasm for strengthening febrile case management and surveillance in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic (62). The core systems that enable timely treatment and optimal resource allocation for malaria are the same networks that can increase the visibility of emerging febrile disease threats (63). Prior investments through the Global Fund to strengthen diagnosis, enhance surveillance systems, train public health workers, and improve community case management for malaria, HIV, and tuberculosis also contribute meaningfully to building capacity to detect and respond to other public health emergencies (64). Building on this foundation through an expanded donor base can strengthen the necessary infrastructure for diagnosis of febrile disease, provide treatment for the illnesses that cause a heavy burden of child mortality, and enable extensive disease surveillance to improve understanding of what is happening and how governments can respond early. Whether the COVID-19 pandemic successfully sparks meaningful investments in systems that could relieve the financial pressure on malaria budgets remains to be seen. Similar

calls for health systems investment were made in the aftermath of Ebola virus disease outbreaks in West Africa in 2014-15 but failed to fully materialize once the epidemic was no longer a visible threat (65).

Increase cost-effectiveness through surveillance-driven strategies. As budgets tighten, the focus of malaria programs will necessarily evolve from providing protection to everyone with any level of risk towards reducing malaria to the greatest extent possible given the resources available. This idea is the core of the High Burden, High Impact strategy launched by WHO and the Roll Back Malaria Partnership (66), which brought cutting edge modeling and risk mapping support to the countries with the most malaria cases to help them to identify cost-optimal intervention packages to fund with their Global Fund grants. As bed net coverage has increased, nets have been overallocated to certain households while missing others (26, 27), potentially leading to a discordance between who is protected and who is at highest risk of malaria (67). Targeting interventions to those at highest risk (i.e., aiming for high coverage within specific priority locations) can theoretically have substantially greater impact on malaria transmission than untargeted distribution (68), although empirical evidence of such impact is still lacking (69). The potential of a targeted approach is highlighted by the attribution of the successes of the smallpox eradication campaign to a shift from universal coverage (i.e., mass vaccination) to targeted strategies that greatly reduced the population receiving vaccine but achieved high coverage in the specific places where it would have the greatest impact (70).

Any targeting plan would need to be devised by governmental programs on a local basis, but consideration of population distributions across malaria endemicities provides a sense of the opportunities for better targeting to affect malaria budgets. About 90% of the 1.1 billion people in sub-Saharan Africa live in areas with some malaria risk (Fig. 4). Targeting tools for prevention such as bed nets only to those who live in areas that had a prevalence >10% in 2000 (before the start of intervention scale up and thus a proxy for areas of intrinsic risk in the absence of intervention) would reduce the population to be covered to 836 million. Targeting only those in the highest risk places, where prevalence was once >50%, would focus on the 333 million people living in those geographies.

Successfully improving the cost effectiveness and sustainability of our strategies will only be feasible with high quality intelligence on malaria and intervention coverage. Although

surveillance is a core pillar of the WHO's Global Technical Strategy launched in 2015 (11), it is arguably less important under a universal coverage strategy than one that seeks to target interventions efficiently. Strengthening surveillance systems and analytic capacity within endemic country governments and local research institutions will require allocating additional resources in the near term. Those resources should prioritize routine in-country data collection and use, and enable incorporation of more advanced approaches such as genomic surveillance and mathematical modelling. Digitization of data systems and improved geospatial infrastructure can put at-risk populations on the map and increase accountability by visualizing programmatic gaps. Demonstrable improvements in data quality can give programs more confidence to target and tailor resources accordingly (71). Near-term investments in data quality may therefore prove cost-efficient over the long term as they enable more impactful use of available malaria funding. For example, improvements in entomological surveillance enable programs to understand where different types of mosquito vector resistance to various products occurs, and thus where next generation nets and insecticides can be cost-effective despite being more expensive than current products (72).

Strengthen health systems. Universal access to diagnosis and prompt effective treatment is an important component of the first pillar of the WHO's Global Technical Strategy (11). Besides its importance for treating illness, increasing coverage of curative treatment for sick individuals may reduce malaria incidence (73) and decrease malaria transmission by curing infections (74). Empirical measurement of case management quality and its effects can be challenging (75), but increasing routine treatment rates may have caused about 20% of the decline in malaria prevalence in Africa since 2000 (23). These reductions could result from replacing ineffective drugs with effective ones (76, 77), increasing treatment-seeking practices (78), or improving access to quality case management services (79).

Today, the quality and coverage of appropriate routine treatment of malaria illness is highly variable both between (80) and within (81) countries. The fraction of malaria fevers in sub-Saharan Africa estimated to receive an ACT in 2015 ranged from 0.6% in Somalia to 70.2% in Uganda, with an average of only 20% (82). Population surveys conducted over the past two decades suggest blood testing has increased and most anti-malarial drugs received are now effective ACTs. However, treatment-seeking for febrile illness has remained flat and

considerable numbers of illnesses are still not managed appropriately (Fig. 5). Given that malaria treatment is provided through health systems that are usually not malaria-specific, health system strengthening in pursuit of universal health coverage offers an opportunity to drive progress without depending fully on constrained malaria budgets. Doing so will require better understanding of how treatment of patients varies according to factors such as the accessibility of health services to at-risk populations, their perceived quality, and availability and affordability of appropriate drugs. Careful monitoring and evaluation of routine treatment coverage at a sub-national level would allow malaria programs to identify where insufficient fractions of malaria cases are being cured to better understand why such gaps persist and how interventions, such as expansion of community health worker networks, can best be designed to increase coverage. Stronger health systems may also enable more routine delivery of vector control tools, which could reduce donor funding requirements (83).

Fig 5. Case management practices over time. National results from all available Demographic Health Surveys since 2000 (as reported at www.statcompiler.com) are depicted for the fraction of respondents reporting seeking treatment for febrile childhood illness in the prior two weeks,

the fraction receiving a blood test if treatment was sought, and the fraction of antimalarial drugs received that were ACTs.

Engage the private sector. Analysis of population surveys (84) suggests a substantial portion of nets in certain countries including Kenya and Angola are purchased rather than received through donor-funded distributions. Most of these bed nets (country median = 77%) were insecticide-treated (84), though more detailed information on quality and whether they may represent leakage from public sector distributions was not available. Still, the persistence of a market for bed nets despite ongoing free mass distribution suggests the potential for a hybrid strategy to maintain coverage (85). Willingness-to-pay studies find almost half of middle-income households in Ghana (86) and majorities in Nigeria (87) would be willing to purchase their own nets. Encouraging those who can afford to purchase vector control tools to do so while targeting donor funds to vulnerable groups who truly require subsidized or free tools, potentially including vouchers (88) or surveillance-driven targeting within poor, underserved communities, could be important for maximizing coverage and ensuring donor funds are used to provide protection to those most in need of it. The potential for a market approach was demonstrated by the voucher subsidy Tanzania introduced in 2004 (89), but little recent evidence exists given the ubiquity of donor-funded mass bed net distribution.

Similarly, private drug shops, pharmacies, and clinics are an important source of malaria care throughout many highly endemic countries (19), but little public investment is made in improving the quality of care in this sector. For example, a recent survey in Nigeria found that, of the 73% of febrile children for whom caregivers sought treatment, 37% went to the public sector, while 58% attended a private sector outlet including drug shops and pharmacies (90). Ignoring private outlets in such a context thus greatly limits the fraction of malarial illnesses that can be identified and cured. Prior efforts to strengthen private sector case management have included mass subsidies of ACTs (91) as well as more targeted approaches to improve case management practices (92).

Investment in non-commodity-based approaches and transformative technologies. Cyclical campaign delivery of insecticide-based commodities does not change the intrinsic risk of malaria, and thus must be continued in perpetuity to avoid a resurgence of malaria. Interventions that more permanently reduce human-vector breeding contact may thus be important near-term

investments for long-term gains. Such approaches, which must be designed and implemented by those expert in local contexts, would also build the environmental and structural resilience necessary to sustain the gains catalyzed by commodities such as bed nets and insecticides, especially during the increasing future challenges that can be expected as climate-related disruptions worsen.

There is a substantial body of evidence that housing improvements including screening windows and eaves may reduce malaria prevalence (93) and incidence while also reducing incidence of other mosquito-borne diseases (94). Despite the inclusion of housing improvements in the Abuja Declaration and a subsequent consensus statement from Roll Back Malaria and the United Nations Development Programme calling housing improvements an “important and sustainable component in the global effort for malaria control and elimination” (95), they are not typically included within intervention packages today. Similarly, efforts to reduce breeding sites, once a core component of anti-malarial efforts (96) and still practiced extensively in countries including the United States (97), fell out of favor with scale up of insecticidal, commodified measures that are minimally tailored to local contexts. Though not recommended in all situations, larval source management may present meaningful opportunities in certain settings where breeding sites are not too extensive (98). These sorts of approaches are not simple for a health system to deploy, nor necessarily as cost-effective as tools like bed nets. Yet efforts undertaken by government ministries outside the health sector, such as programs aimed at improving housing quality or sanitation, might still contribute to reductions in malaria, and would represent local solutions to local problems. Encouraging actors such as the agricultural and mining sectors, as well as communities themselves, to reduce breeding sites or improve housing quality could be pursued through a combination of subsidies, taxes, education, and legislation.

Investment in transformative technologies must also continue to develop the next-generation tools and strategies that can more effectively achieve sustainable gains against malaria.

Promising tools for preventing malaria in the future include highly efficacious, long-lasting vaccines (99), chemoprevention (100), and monoclonal antibodies (101). Technologies such as genetically modified mosquitoes and other biological means of modifying mosquito populations hold potential for transforming malaria control as well (102). While these future technologies may be required for the ultimate goal of malaria eradication, they should be pursued in parallel

with efforts to use today's tools as effectively as possible. As Hackett wrote in 1937, our "duty is to fight the disease now with weapons already proved useful, albeit imperfect, rather than to fold the hands while awaiting a problematical *therapia magna* of the future" (103).

Conclusions

Before submitting proposals for Global Fund resources, endemic countries are required to devise a National Strategic Plan that describes the interventions they would ideally like to implement. Typically, the price tag for these plans is far higher than the resource envelope available from the Global Fund, PMI, and domestic budgets. For example, Nigeria calculated a total funding need of \$1.26 billion for 2018-2020 with a potential unfunded gap of \$180 million after adding up available domestic and donor allocations. Given this shortfall, national malaria programs go through a prioritization exercise to decide what the highest priority budget items are, and which components of their strategy will go unfunded. The global malaria community today finds itself in an analogous situation: the annual price tag of nearly \$9 billion by 2030 for its universal coverage strategy is nearly three times higher than the funding available today. Advocating for donors to fill that gap is appropriate given the considerable cost-effectiveness of investments in malaria, but simultaneously it is critical to plan a strategy that optimizes the funding that is committed in reality.

The numbers for the coming years are daunting. They suggest that further progress against malaria using current strategies— which are responsible for saving the lives of millions — is unlikely in the absence of another step change in the amount of funding available to malaria programs and the health systems within which they are grounded. This critical juncture comes even as the continued pursuit of universal coverage through bed nets, indoor residual spraying, and seasonal malaria chemoprevention campaigns may be increasingly challenged by severe weather, social upheaval, and population movement. To address these challenges, the global malaria community, led by the WHO and aligned within the Roll Back Malaria partnership, has begun to take steps towards shifting its approach to a more data-driven, efficient strategy that has the potential to make the math work. These efforts mark an important step away from the universal coverage strategies that are now providing increasingly diminishing returns. At the same time, however, truly changing course appears to require more extensive changes.

Given population growth and rising commodity prices, malaria programs will have no choice but to embrace resource optimization approaches that target resources more carefully and give priority to protecting those most in need and at highest risk. The malaria community needs to proactively channel more of its funding into strengthening general health systems – including those beyond the direct oversight of malaria-specific programs – to provide sustainable access to quality case management services, rather than relying primarily on vertical campaign delivery channels. Governments will need to embrace means of providing services that leverage resources beyond donor funds, such as the private case management sector and out-of-pocket expenditure for protective tools by those who can truly afford it. Today’s strategies must be supplemented with multi-sectoral approaches that can transform malaria transmission dynamics by improving housing quality and removing vector breeding sites. These changes will require critical improvements in data systems that can provide the information that is critical to making wise decisions with limited budgets.

The pursuit of quick wins through campaign delivery of bed nets to protect the most vulnerable has evolved and expanded into continual cycles of vertical interventions with the goal of universal coverage. These aspirations, laudable though they are and as effective as they have been in preventing morbidity and mortality, will draw increasingly out of reach as populations grow and prices increase in the absence of substantial increases in funding. It is increasingly urgent to evolve our malaria control strategy to strengthen and better use surveillance systems for decision-making, reinforce health systems to ensure high coverage of quality case management, engage the private sector and other alternative delivery channels, and invest in a broader array of community-driven approaches to reduce malaria. Each of these ideas can be found in the Abuja declaration written more than 20 years ago. The success of this third decade of the modern era of malaria control depends on whether these ideas are finally realized.

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